

COMPARISON BETWEEN RECTANGULAR PROPORTIONS: GOLDEN VERSUS ROOT RATIO.

PRODUCTS TO BUDDHIST TEMPLES STRUCTURES - RESEARCH ABOUT PREFERENCES OF RECTANGLE'S PROPORTIONS IN KOREAN DESIGN.

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ABSTRACT

This paper is based on empirically revealed doubts on the universal preference of the golden ratio proportion. An empirical study has been conducted in order to examine differences about 'preferences of proportions' on the golden ratio between South Korean and Western preceding studies by Kimberly Elam's "Geometry of Design: Studies in Proportion and Composition".

Proportions are determined by mathematical logic, however 'preferred proportions' arise from cultural influences and experience. The research was conducted with two hundred subjects between the ages of twenty to thirty in Korea, with questions that showed ten choices of different proportions of rectangles. The data of comparisons clearly revealed that Korean had a preference to root proportion (1:1.414). These results obviously contradict previous studies conducted in the Western culture showed preferences of the golden ratio (1:1.618) (Benjafield, 1979, 2010; Pittard, 2007).

The aspect of the results will provide deeper insights of the influence of the design process in specifically on the design form. The paper continues to examine and introduce various Korean traditional and modern objects, architectural structures that exemplify the research results. The paper concludes that various examples of root proportions can be found in Korean design environment showing a Korean preference for root ratio reflecting the here presented results.

Keywords: golden ratio, root ratio, preferred proportions, cultural preference, design form

INTRODUCTION

This research started with the question why western society prefers the golden ratio. With the readings and findings of Gustav Fechner (Fechner, 1876) the

interest to analyze Korean preferred proportions arouse. Especially, the questions which factors do reflect esthetics and how might these perceptions are universal in terms of were do standards begin. Hence, this study recognizes systems of proportions, influenced by masterpieces, famous artists and aesthetic progress as much mathematical progress. This paper then examines the differences in culture and their preference in proportions, and in doing so this research tries to establish a new design principle exempt from western proportions and the possibility of a new understanding of visual education.

FECHNER EXPERIMENTS

The golden ratio can be found throughout the Western world, organizing architecture and design starting from ancient times till present day. In 1865 Gustav Fechner, a German physicist, was curious about the golden ratio aiming to explain esthetics through mathematics. Fechner conducted one of the first famous experiments on proportions.

[1] Ten rectangles that were used by Gustav Fechner's experiments

In Fechner's experiments ten different sizes of rectangles were shown to participants and they were asked, which one they preferred. Fechner's interest in esthetics arouse by the idea that typical esthetic preferences between cultures might exist. Hence, Fechner continued his research findings on objects, in particular, which had rectangular shapes and found that the average was always close to the golden ration (1:1.618). Moreover, with questioning

people on these objects, people preferences steered towards objects that kept those proportions.

[2] Lalo result on comparisons on rectangle preferences.

Lalo (1908) repeated Fechner’s experiments and indicated the same results as other researchers after him, that people preferred objects with the golden ratio.

ANALYSIS OF WESTERN PRODUCTS

In the following we present products and architecture and analyze them in relation to the golden ratio. We chose examples of classical western product designs and architecture in chronological order to later compare with Korean classical products and architecture.

FURNITURE

[3] Golden ratio: Renaissance and Baroque style furniture Proportion can be analyzed in furniture design. The first examples of golden proportion are closets from the Baroque and Renaissance period. The layout of the furniture illustrates the geometrical planes that are divided into two parts each surface exemplifying a golden proportion (Jung, 2007).

MODERN PRODUCTS

Also in modern products the golden ratio seems to play an important role. For example looking at cars the body of the Volkswagen Beetle by Kimberly Elam (2001), a car once shown to people that was most liked in the Western society; fits perfectly to the ellipse of the golden ratio were the major axis perfectly fits with the bottom of the car.

[4] Analysis of golden ratio with a Volkswagen Beetle

ARCHITECTURE

In architecture, the Parthenon Temple in Greece analyzed by Kimberly Elam (2001) is one of the strongest examples of the golden proportions. The Temple façade of the Parthenon is embraced by a subdivided golden rectangle and a reciprocal rectangle forms the height of the architrave, frieze, and pediment.

[5] Golden ratio: Parthenon Temple in Greece

METHOD

Fechner's and Lalo's experiments were conducted in the Western world and as far as the authors know, no similar experiments were performed in Asian countries. Hence, in 2006 the same experiments of Fechner and Lalo were conducted with Korean subjects for a comparison on preferences of rectangle proportions.

SUBJECTS

A total of 200 South Korean subjects participated in the experiment. Subjects were selected randomly through individual interviews or gathered by asking groups of people to participate in the experiment. Subjects' ages ranged from 20's to 30's were they consist of 100 male and 100 female. The amount of subjects was selected due to the interest if there is a difference of outcome between female and male, therefore half of each gender of subjects were selected.

QUESTIONNAIRE

The questionnaire had two parts. The first part was a choice question composed of ten choices from A to J in alphabetical order. The second part was made up to ask the subjects on "personal specifications": personal height, age, gender, and profession. These specifications were particular considered due to the potential influence with the preferences of proportions. Where the first part was hidden from the second part to decrease the influence to the subject.

PROCEDURE

The participants were given ten different sizes of rectangles shapes at once without a particular order. The subjects were able to interact with the shapes on a table for a few minutes. After that time the participants were asked individually what ratio they felt most comfortable with. The participants did not know what the experiment was about.

RESULTS

Korean's preference overall liked shorter ratios, a significant difference to results of experiments conducted in the west.

[6] Korea result on comparisons on rectangle preferences

The graph demonstrates on the x-axis ten different rectangle proportions that were presented to the subjects and on the y-axis the percentage of preference. The result revealed that 15.5 % preferred the root ratio of 1:1.414 and 14.5 % preferred a perfect square (1:1).

ANALYSIS OF KOREAN PRODUCTS

This paper tries to explain through visual principles of geometric compositions of wide selection of products, and buildings that are visualized and analyzed by these principles. The products that were selected for analysis are considered as classical design in Korea. These designs are presented in chronological order with the relationship to proportions and design of the time.

FURNITURE

[7] Analysis of root 2 with Korean traditional furniture from the Joseon Dynasty (1413 - 1865)

Korean traditional furniture, illustrated here by a closet from the Joseon Dynasty is divided into the upper part and lower part surfaces with root 2 rectangles.

[8] Analysis of root 2 with Korean traditional grain storage. Similarly, analysis was done in root 2 proportions and found in ancient Korean grain storage (Jung, 2007). These proportions differ to previous illustrated Baroque and Renaissance surfaces, which clearly showed a golden ratio.

MODERN PRODUCTS

Similar analyses were done with modern Korean products. Stated by a Korean design research group the Ssangyong New-Korando exemplifies Korean car design.

[9] Analysis of root 2 of Ssangyong New-Korando

The car analyzed shows root 2 ellipse that are inscribed in a root 2 rectangle construction diagram. The car fits cleanly in the top half of this root 2 ellipse. The major axis of the ellipse aligns with the body with the center of the tires.

[10] Kim-chi refrigerator in Korea, analysis of root 2 proportions. Another analysis was performed on Korean *Kim-chi* refrigerators. The *Kim-chi* refrigerator is specific to Korean culture needs. The refrigerator aligned its surface on a root 2 rectangle (Jung, 2007).

ARCHITECTURE

Geometrical proportions in architecture can be widely observed through regulation lines that dictate the placement of doors, windows and their proportions to the façade. Therefore, the analysis of Korean cultural heritage architecture and layouts add an important part to this study.

[11] Analysis of ancient Korean residential (Mumum pottery period) area through root 2

The layouts of ancient Korean residential houses were analyzed and observed to be laid out on $\sqrt{2}$ proportions. These houses were from the Mumum pottery period that is known for the origin of intensive agriculture and complex societies in Korea.

[12] Traditional Korean temple, analysis of root 2 proportions (1626)

Further proof of root 2 proportions through Korean architecture can be found in the analysis of traditional Korean temples, where the regulating lines to the relationship of construction diagrams are root 2 section rectangles.

[13] Traditional Korean door analysis of root 2

In a simple analysis the façade and the interiors, for example the traditional Korean door, is embraced by a subdivided root 2 rectangle.

[14] Seoul Twin Tower, root 2 analysis (1987)

Even today, modern Korean architecture as the analysis showed is represented here by the Twin Towers in Seoul the regulating lines of the construction diagrams are proportioned by $\sqrt{2}$ (Jung, 2007).

COMPARISONS ON HUMAN SCALE

After the results of various analyses on proportions of Korean and Western products and architecture, it is interesting to further explore the relationship between the Korean and Western human scale.

[15] Vitruvius face ratio analyzed to the golden ratio

One of these examples is the Vitruvius face by Kimberly Elam (2001) that observes the golden ratio through dividing rectangles showing proportions of face, eyes, lips and the chin. Facial proportion analysis is according to Vitruvius canon, and the proportions are almost identical. The diagram shows a single golden section rectangle as the guide for the length and width of the head. This golden rectangle is further subdivided by a smaller golden section rectangle to determine the placement of the features.

[16] Buddhist figure analyzed with root rectangles

This analysis was compared with a similar process to the Korean Buddha figure (Jung, 2007). This Buddha figure demonstrated a root 2 proportion with face, eyes, lips and the chin through smaller rectangles. This spurred more interest why these differences exist between Western and Korean culture.

[18] Analysis of traditional Indian dance position with root 2 by Robert Lawlor (1982)

Summarizing, we can state that based on the empirical data analyses of Korean preferences as well as based on the analyses of product and architectural examples, Korean people prefer root 2 rectangle proportions. These results, if we can generalize them, have two implications:

1. Korean prefers other proportions than Western cultures.
2. The golden ratio proportion is not a general preference of all human beings but seems to be culturally influenced.

[17] Comparing proportions between Western and Eastern bodies

The illustration of body proportions in the Western culture was analyzed and found that the center point was different compared to the Korean body proportions illustration by Robert Lawlor (1982). In the Western culture the ratio of the body is divided through each point by the belly button, knee and armpits, which is physically visible. In the Korean proportions, the division of the height of the human body has been represented by the square root of 2. From this perspective, the center of the body is located in the hypogastric center (丹田; Danjoen). It is the place of the body where the inner center is built and sensed that is found in the abdomen about three finger widths below and two fingers widths behind the navel. In Korean tradition, it is considered the physical center of gravity of the human body and is the seat of one's internal energy.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study we tried to analysis a so-called principle of formative arts, the golden ratio. An empirical investigation, which was a repetition of Fechner's experiment, has been done to explore possible differences between the East and the West about a sense of proportion that is affected by not physical needs but also internal satisfaction concerning the proportion of design principles. A proportion is determined by mathematical logic, but preferring a proportion is steered by learning and experience. Showing that Korean people do not prefer the golden ratio, which is preferred by Western cultures, leads to the necessity to assess and define 'preferring proportion' anew. Furthermore, Korean subjects' preferred proportion should be considered as one of the essential elements of formative arts for the design identity of Korean culture. And furthermore, systematic research of our preferences of proportion (root ratio) in various fields should be done.

REFERENCES

- Benjafield, John. (1976). The 'Golden Rectangle': Some New Data, *American Journal of Psychology*, 89 (4, Dec.), 737-43.
- Benjafield, J. G. (2010), The golden section and American psychology, 1892-1938. *Journal of the History of the Behavioral Sciences*, 46: 52-71.
- Elam, Kimberly. (2001). *Geometry of Design: Studies in Proportion and Composition*, Princeton Architectural Press, USA.
- Fechner, G. T. (1876). *Vorschule der Aesthetik*. Leipzig: Von Breitkopf & Hartel.
- Lalo, Charles. (1908). *L'estehtique experimentale de Fechner*. Ph.D. diss. (These pour le doctorat es lettres) Universite de Paris. Paris: Felix Alcan.
- Lawlor, Robert. (1982). *Sacred Geometry: Philosophy and Practice*, London and New York: Thames & Hudson.
- Pittard, N., Ewing, M., Jevons, C. (2007). Aesthetic theory and logo design: examining consumer response to proportion across cultures. *International Marketing Review*, Vol. 24 Iss: 4, pp. 457-473
- Jung, J.Y., Munn, M.K. (2007). A Study on Proportion of the Traditional Structures at Buddhist Temple based on Rectangle Preference Proportion, Visual analysis through $\sqrt{2}$ Rectangle. Master's degree thesis, Korea University of Technology and Education, Korea.